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RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND INCLUSIVE GROWTH: HIGHER EDUCATION FOR WOMEN LEADING TO RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND INCLUSIVE GROWTH

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Abstract:

In the global economy, each economy has experienced a different growth in the economy all together. Inclusive growth is not possible unless we have a collective effort from both government and private participation. Inclusive growth is not a short term process it involves a continues effort. Thus it is a long term goal. Thus to have a perfect inclusive growth there need to be a growth in education and human resource, especially education in the rural areas women. The success of education in rural areas in women has a link to various positive aspect it has a link towards the nations growth. On the other hand human resource is the important aspect which majority of our economy stressing upon. The human development index has shown how Indian economy is performing past from many years being compared with the other nations in the world. From the collective effort, basically we need to strengthen the foundation of our economy in order to reach the success, thus India is now all set to have an inclusive growth with the hope of getting a positive impact on the economy.

Key Words: *Economy, Inclusive Growth, Rural Development*

Introduction:

Our economy has over the last six decades of experience which has seen the growth of Indian economy in different stages altogether, Is now ready to enter a different kind of growth, that is one marked by a high rate of expansion, combined with 'inclusive growth.' in recent years inclusive growth is one of the hot topic which was sponsored even from national and international agency, Asian development banks, world bank etc. even though the past government has taken a number of initiatives for the successive implementation of the term so called inclusive growth" it is just not enough when we compare with the size and the scale of operation in Indian scenario, thus for this not only the government but the participation of the private sector is equally important. Thus both government and private sector all together play a significant role in driving the inclusive growth.

When we proudly say about "shining India" we are ignoring various factors, even though India is suffering from various issues, Especially rural development. Indian land is majorly covered by rural areas. When we think big we need to do big.... One of the hurdles that we

are right now is the rural development. Many government initiatives has already implemented in the rural areas in order to have a good plan for rural development, to some extent these plan have been a success. The way left for the effective and long term growth of the rural areas is concentrating on the higher education especially on women in rural areas. Experts do believe this as a effective tool for the inclusive growth.

Objective

The objective of this paper is to analyze the importance of women getting higher education in rural areas and its link to inclusive growth in Indian context.

Methodology used:

The analysis in this paper has been done on the basis of the secondary data collected from published source. As paper focuses mainly on higher education in women and the inclusive growth the relevant data are taken from various published article from government, non government report est.

Scope of the study:

The paper focus's on Inclusive growth and its need for the inclusive growth in Indai with summery of finding including various hurdle for the collective successes for inclusive growth

Inclusive growth:

Inclusive growth refers *both* to the pace and pattern of growth, which are considered interlinked, and therefore in need to be addressed together. The idea that both the pace and pattern of growth are critical for achieving a high, sustainable growth record, as well as poverty reduction, is consistent with the findings in the *Growth Report: Strategies for Sustained Growth and Inclusive Development* (Commission on Growth and Development, 2008). The commission notes that inclusiveness – a concept that encompasses equity, equality of opportunity, and protection in market and employment transitions – is an essential ingredient of any successful growth strategy. Here we emphasize the idea of equality of opportunity in terms of access to markets, resources, and unbiased regulatory environment for businesses and individuals.⁴ The Commission on Growth and Development (2008) considers systematic inequality of opportunity “toxic” as it will derail the growth process through political channels or conflict. The inclusive growth approach takes a longer term perspective as the focus is on productive employment rather than on direct income redistribution, as a means of increasing incomes for excluded groups. In the short run, governments could use income distribution schemes to attenuate negative impacts on the poor of policies intended to jump start growth, but transfer schemes cannot be an answer in the long run and can be problematic also in the short run.⁵ In poor countries such schemes can impose significant burdens on already stretched budgets, and it is theoretically impossible to reduce poverty through redistribution in countries where average income falls below US\$ 700 per year.

Need for inclusive growth in India:

Inclusive growth is necessary for sustainable development and equitable distribution of wealth and prosperity. Achieving inclusive growth is the biggest challenge in a country like India. In a democratic country like India, bringing 600 million people living in rural India into the mainstream is the biggest concern. The challenge is to take the levels of growth to all section of the society and to all parts of the country. The best way to achieve inclusive growth is through developing people's skills. Mr. Jeffrey, Chairman & CEO of Manpower Planning,

USA, said that , a multifaceted approach towards education and skills development is necessary to achieve grow. He said the challenge of skills shortage can be addressed through public private partnership. Since independence, significant improvement in India's economic and social development made the nation to grow strongly in the 21st century. The following factors encouraged the India to concentrate more on inclusive growth

- India is the 7th largest country by area and 2nd by population. It is the 12th largest economy at market exchange rate and 4th largest by PPP. Yet, India is far away from the development of the neighborhood nation, i.e., China.
- The exclusion in terms of low agriculture growth, low quality employment growth, low human development, rural-urban divides, gender and social inequalities, and regional disparities etc. are the problems for the nation. • Reducing of poverty and other disparities and raising of economic growth are the key objectives of the nation through inclusive growth.
- Political leadership in the country plays a vital role in the overall development of the country. But, the study has found that politicians in India have a very low level of scientific literacy.
- Studies estimated that the cost of corruption in India amounts to over 10% of GDP. Corruption is one of the ills that prevent inclusive growth.
- Although child labor has been banned by the law in India and there are stringent provisions to deter this inhuman practice. Still, many children in India are unaware of education as their lives are spoiled to labour work.
- Literacy levels have to rise to provide the skilled workforce required for higher growth.
- Economic reforms in the country are overwhelmed by out dated philosophies and allegations by the politicians and opposition parties in India.
- Achievement of 9% of GDP growth for country as a whole is one of the boosting factor which gives the importance to the Inclusive growth in India.
- Inclusiveness benchmarked against achievement of monitorable targets related to (i). Income & Poverty, (ii) education, (iii) health, & human resource (iv) women & children, (v) infrastructure, (vi) environment.
- Even at international level also, there is a concern about inequalities and exclusion and now they are also taking about inclusive approach for development.

Summary of findings:

Rural India constitutes 72.2% of the population. Due to increased literacy rate these sectors will see greater developments. Thus if the base root will have a stronger strength then in reality inclusive growth is possible. Here the strong root is “higher education for women” it’s true that the education will have a greater positive effect on the economy, especially higher education will lead to increase in the standard of living among the people, national income, per capita income and then it will lead to overall development of the economy, and it will lay a strong foundation for competing in the international level as well.

According to office of registrar general of India, ministry of home affairs India including the union territory’s as a whole has recorded for a literacy rate is 82.14% in male and 65.46% in female, which clearly indicates that India is lagging behind in education for women. That is why before talking to higher education in women there is a need to think and talk about the basic education for women. Definitely it is a true fact that not all state in India do have low literacy rate. We need to have a clear differentiation between literacy rate and the higher education rate, only in recent years the Higher education has taken its grip in the economy due to heavy competition from globalised economy. Out of the literacy people the people who opt for the higher education is just within 20%. there could be various reason for stoppage of education, like financial problem, lack of guidance, no proper government support in term of education loan to the needy students etc. when analyze the literacy rate of Karnataka it is 82.85% in male and 68.13% in female and in Udupi it is 86.29% in male

and 91.69% in female and in Dakshina kannada it is 88.62% in male and 93.3% in female is the literacy rate.

It is very essential that the economy needs to be strengthened by any means of action, for that the term inclusive growth. If both government as well as the private participants initiatives are essential. In spite of India having a literacy rate of 74% students on average drop out of secondary education every year. But, education sector will see tremendous growth due to increasing demand of quality students. Major reforms will be seen only if the importance given to higher education with an increase in collaboration of foreign universities

Challenges of Higher education for women leading to rural development and inclusive growth:

Defiantly the thought of higher education for women leading to the rural development is an wonderful thought but while implementing it we will have to face a lot of social, economic hurdle as such, because the task of inclusive growth is not at all easy to achieve. The strong focused decision has to be taken by the government, in the mean time the importance has to be given to all the states equally and the government must try to collaborate this work from the support of the major player in the private sectors with the joint venture, or initiation by the private sector to adopt a particular rural area for the purpose of helping that particular rural people to have a good higher education focusing to women for inclusive growth est. the above mentioned task is happening in India but only for the sake of doing the corporate social responsibility by the private people. When we compare our effort with that of another country the initiation taken at Egypt, Asia, and China are really a successful story all together. Thus even in India we can adopt such initiation to have a development in higher education especially in women among the rural areas.

Collective efforts for inclusive growth:

The topic focuses from an macro perspective but in reality the collective effort for the inclusive growth need to be done on the basis of micro perspective. The reality is that for the size of India, it will be foolishnesses from the part of ours if we don't let our effort for this. Not only government is responsible for the inclusive growth in India it is the responsibility of each and every citizen of India. When both government and private organization will look at the inclusive growth then defiantly it can be solved to a greater extent. Infrastructure, education, health est. play a critical role in increasing the standard of India. In that the education especially the higher education today will be a greater positive tool for the real strengthening of inclusive growth.

Human resource:

While concentrating on inclusive growth, a major factor to be examined is the socio-economic inclusiveness of the people. Inclusive growth being a long term process necessarily emanates from the inclusive nature of socio-economic development across regions and people. As per the UNDP Human Development Report 2009 (HRD 2009), India ranked 134 out of 182 countries of the world placing it at the same rank as in 2006 (the Human Development Index (HDI) for India in 2007 was 0.612).⁷ However, the HDI value of India has increased gradually from 0.427 in 1980 to 0.556 in 2000 and went up to 0.612 in 2007, but it is still in the medium Human Development category with even countries like China, Sri Lanka and Indonesia having better ranking. In fact, India lags behind in various social indicators of development. There is a huge gap between India and developed world and even many developing countries in respect of health and education, which needs to be bridged at a faster pace. According to HDR, life expectancy at birth in India was 63.4 years in 2007 as against 80.5 years in Norway, 81.4 years in Australia, 74.0 years in Sri Lanka and 72.9 years in China. Adult literacy rate (aged 15 and above) in 1999-2007 was 66.0 per cent in India as against near 100 per cent in China and 92.0 per cent in Indonesia. In the case of combined gross enrolment ratio in education also India was much below the level achieved by some other comparable countries, like China, Norway, and Thailand etc.

Thus to summarize the above narration not only education but also the stability in human resource need to be maintained for the inclusive growth.

Human Development Index

Country	1980	1985	1990	1995	2000	2005	2006	2007
Poland	0.806	0.823	0.853	0.871	0.876	0.88
Brazil	0.685	0.694	0.71	0.734	0.79	0.805	0.808	0.813
Russia	0.821	0.777	...	0.804	0.811	0.817
Turkey	0.628	0.674	0.705	0.73	0.758	0.796	0.802	0.806
Thailand	0.658	0.684	0.706	0.727	0.753	0.777	0.78	0.783
China	0.533	0.556	0.608	0.657	0.719	0.756	0.763	0.772
Sri Lanka	0.649	0.67	0.683	0.696	0.729	0.752	0.755	0.759
Indonesia	0.522	0.562	0.624	0.658	0.673	0.723	0.729	0.734
Vietnam	...	0.561	0.599	0.647	0.69	0.715	0.72	0.725
Egypt	0.496	0.552	0.58	0.631	0.665	0.696	0.7	0.703
India	0.427	0.453	0.489	0.511	0.556	0.596	0.604	0.612

Source: Human Development Report, 2009

Internationally the condition of India is not very sound as mention in above table. Other problems are labour, child labour, 'bandhs' (forcible closure of shops, offices & transport), etc. are the major challenge on the path of inclusive growth. Exploitation of labour is widely prevalent. Despite the promulgation of minimum wages, the feudal system in the rural areas and industry in the urban conglomerates continue to fleece labour, paying them wages far below those prescribed. In certain areas, politicians and political parties have their own vested interests in keeping people poor and deprived. They have a ready-made electoral constituency which they fear losing with education and prosperity. Certain other vested interests would like to persist with the caste system to sustain their political base.¹⁰ No growth can be inclusive unless it takes adequate care of women and children.

Child labour, despite a plethora of laws and India's commitments at the ILO, is still unfortunately very much prevalent. Just this month (June, 2008), the British clothing major Primark has axed its three Indian suppliers for allegedly using child labour to finish clothes sold in Britain's high streets. The fashion chain says that it has cancelled all orders from the three companies based in the Tirapur region of Tamil Nadu and removed all their garments from its shelves. Child labour has been banned by law in India and there are stringent provisions to deter this inhuman practice. But numbers tell a different story – there are an estimated 60 million child labourers in India, but there have been only 670,000 violations of the law detected in eight years and just 22,588 convictions. Millions of young children continue to work in roadside eateries, glass factories, carpet looms or sweeping and cooking in homes in violation of the Child Labor (Prohibition and Regulation) Act. Failure to implement the law and poor rehabilitation policies need urgent attention. While on the one hand an increase in the number of officials and labor inspectors is called for, together with imparting better training and instilling greater sensitivity in them; on the other hand, there is a need to tackle poverty which is the main reason driving parents into pushing their young children to work instead of sending them to schools. This mammoth problem is one of the main challenges to resolve in addressing inclusive growth.

The country's ethos needs to change to bring about an end to child labor, together with a strong political and bureaucratic commitment to end this gory practice. We need to attract children from poverty stricken families to schools. Mid-day meal schemes of Governments have met with partial success. Again, however, lack of transparency has ensured that funds and rations are misappropriated and misused. Literacy levels have to rise to provide the skilled workforce required for higher growth. India has the third largest pool of scientists, engineers and doctors in the world, but it has yet to reach anywhere near its full potential with a majority of its vast population still illiterate or semi-literate. A majority of its population is still seeped in superstition. The caste system is another curse of Indian society. Combine it with religious communalism and you have a deadly combination for economic disaster. Higher allocations for education and the social sectors, complemented by bold and visionary social and political leadership can pave the way for reforms in these sectors.

The Government of India has been paying a lot of attention to social security as part of its inclusive growth agenda. Recently, it introduced a law in parliament to provide social security to unorganized labour. The National Commission for Women is now working on a draft law to provide similar social security to all domestic workers, under which the employer and servant will have to make matching contributions towards a social security fund to be managed by a specially appointed government authority. The employer will have to pay his contribution over and above the salary, likely to be pegged at ten percent of salary. The draft law, which is in the final stages, still has to look at how and who would deposit the money. The law also looks at providing benefits like pension to those domestic helps registered under the scheme for 15 years. Such social schemes deserve strong support and would go a long way in making inclusive growth a reality. In recent years, India has become a country of demonstrations, agitations and 'bandhs'(forcible closure of shops, offices & transport). For the slightest pretext, trains are stopped, buses and private vehicles burnt and offices and business establishments forcibly closed. This leads to unimaginable loss of man hours and economic output, besides loss of confidence of the outside world for making investments. A peaceful and stable environment is a must for sustained foreign and domestic investments. In this regard, one has to look at initiating proper reforms in the criminal justice system, especially in the police. The Supreme Court has time and again reminded the Government of the need to reform the police force. The outdated Police Act of 1861 needs to be replaced with a modern Act. The Police force needs to be made more responsive and accountable. It should no longer be a tool in the hands of corrupt politicians but responsible to the law of the land. Only then would it be able to provide a secure atmosphere for economic activity to prosper and remove age old impediments towards inclusiveness.

Conclusion:

Inclusive growth is particularly important for ADF countries like India. It has two mutually reinforcing objectives. First, rapid and sustainable growth will create and expand economic opportunities. Second, broader access to these opportunities will ensure that members of society can participate in and benefit from growth. For that supported investments in education, infrastructure—roads, water, energy and other services—to help raise productivity, create jobs, reduce poverty and promote trade and investments.

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